

THE ROLE OF PAPER IN THE ART OF CENTRAL ASIAN LITERATURE

Maftuna Kh. Kalbaeva

Senior Lecturer, department of "Miniature and Calligraphy"
National Institute of Arts and Design named after Kamaliddin Behzad,
Tashkent, 100025, Uzbekistan

Orcid: 0009-0007-3540-1903

imaf_planet@mail.ru

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11096463>

Abstract: This article talks about paper, the main material of ancient handwritten books and inscriptions. The article analyzes the history of the origin of paper and its development factors.

Key words: papyrus paper, handwritten book, calligraphy, miniature, Central Asia.

Introduction.

In the long historical past of the peoples of the East, the art of calligraphy and reading books occupies a special place in the cultural heritage that has been created and left for future generations. It is no secret that the origin and development of the art of kitobot existed among the peoples of Central Asia, that is, in today's land of Uzbekistan. Even when there were no ideas about paper and books in the neighboring countries, the Uzbek people had the opportunity to provide the world with unique paper samples. So, the process of creating a book has been known to us for a long time. In the 15th and 16th centuries, the art of reading in Central Asia developed as a branch of craftsmanship, a mature level of fine art. This art was very useful for science lovers of that time, who wrote down their priceless works, ways of life, with the help of skilled calligraphers and painters, and left a valuable legacy for the future in the form of books. The book-making technique occupied a special place in the division of labor in the medieval life, and the art of calligraphy was a professional profession for people. The development of cultural life has increased people's interest and demand for books. This led to the establishment of book production enterprises. Special book-making workshops were established in such cultural centers as Balkh, Herat, Bukhara, Khiva, Samarkand, and Kokand, where book-making techniques were accelerated in order to meet the needs of the people. Not only artistic manuscripts, but also ordinary books are decorated. Amir Temur and his descendants, as well as Alisher Navoi, who is considered a great representative of the people of knowledge and enlightenment, played an incomparable role in the development of this art. "During the time of Timur and Ulugbek, the high skills of calligraphers, muzahibs, painters, painters and scribes created such beautiful examples of decorative manuscripts that they still amaze the whole world." The art of scribal art, calligraphy and painting also developed further during the time of Alisher Navoi, especially in the areas under the rule of the Timurids. At that time, Sultan Ali Mashhadi, the "Sultan of Calligraphers", the founder of the Herat school of miniature art, Kamoliddin Behzod, and the famous master of book decoration, painter Maulana Yori Muzahhib, were the mentors of hundreds of masters who created royal examples of decorated books. Along with Alisher Navoi, Sultan is the ruler of the time in this development Husayn Boyguro's services were also great. Because with the direct initiative of Sultan Husayn Boykara, in addition to the above-mentioned skilled masters, there are many

other great painters such as Mirak Naqqosh, Qasim Ali Mahmud Muzahhib, Shah Muzaffar, Sultan Muhammad, Dost Muhammad, Abdurazzaq, and calligraphers Muhammad ibn Nur, Darvesh. Scholars such as Muhammad Taqi, Muhammad Khandan, and Muhammad ibn Ashar carried out their activities. From the 17th and 18th centuries, book creation began to be carried out with the help of printing molds engraved on stone, i.e. lithography or lithography. The history, development, and analysis of certain aspects of the art of literature have been researched today by these scientists: E.A. Okhunjonov, E.M. Ismoilova¹, M. Rustamov², A. Madraimov³. At the same time, the discovery of paper was very important for the development of the art of literature and the formation and development of universal culture.

Before the discovery of paper, papyrus, leather, parchment, gauze, bone, ceramic, tree bark, and wood were used as materials for manuscript books. Each of these objects had its own importance for a certain period, but they also had some shortcomings and defects. Papyrus, though light, was very delicate, pottery broke very quickly, gauze was prone to decay, and these writing materials became food for insects. Because of this, most of the ancient manuscripts written on these objects have not reached us. This led to the discovery of a new writing material, papyrus paper. In the 7th century, the ancient Greeks mainly used papyrus imported from Egypt. As a plant, papyrus grew mostly in the swampy areas of the Nile. To make papyrus paper, the papyrus rock is cut with a sharp knife and separated from the fibers. The best fiber is obtained from its core. The first type of papyrus paper was intended for books specially prepared for religious and noble people. The second type of paper is papyrus paper of the lowest grade, which is mainly made for the market. The production of paper from calf, lamb, and goat skins as a writing material was first started in the city of Pergamum in the kingdom of Pergamum in Asia Minor. The paper was called parchment after the city where it was produced. This type of paper was extremely valuable in those times. The width of the papyrus intended for writing was 20-23.5 cm. However, they tried to make papers up to 44 cm, but they did not turn out well and caused inconvenience to use. The length of the papyrus scroll was 8-10 meters depending on the size of the text. But 10-meter papyrus scrolls are rarely prepared. Holding such a large papyrus was a burden for the student. Each line has 35 to 40 letters. Since the third century AD, the number of letters in each line has been fixed and their number did not exceed 25. Texts are written in separate columns from right to left. Ready-made papyrus papers are wrapped in coil-like sticks. The ancient Greeks and Romans called such rods pups and omphalos. The student held the paper in his right hand and wrapped his head around the second stick with his left hand while reading. After reading the text completely, it is wrapped again on the first stick. The rolling papers are placed in leather cases of the appropriate size. To make it easy to find a book or manuscript stored in libraries, the title of the book or the title of the text is written on the head of a stick or case wrapped in paper. Over time, papyri began to disappear due to reckless

¹ Ismoilova E.M. Manuscript book of Central Asia of the late period. Decoration techniques and illustrations. Abstract of the dissertation of Doctor of Historical Sciences. T. 1990.

² Rustamov M. Uzbek book. T. Uzbekistan. 1968.

³ Madraimov.A. The manuscripts of Alisher Navoi's works are an important source of the history of Central Asian literature in the 15th-16th centuries. History of science.dr.diss.abstract.T. 2002.

use. The papyri in the Nile Delta began to dry out and then completely disappear. By the 10th century, papyrus papers were almost out of use. By our time, papyrus is grown in the southern parts of Africa - tropical regions. Over time, parchment paper appeared as the main competitor of papyrus paper. According to legends, there was a serious competition between the ruler of Egypt, Ptolemy, and the ruler of Pergamum, Eumenes, in writing and collecting books. In this regard, Ptolemy, the ruler of Egypt, strictly forbids the export of papyrus from Egypt in order to create an obstacle for Eumenes, the ruler of Pergamum, to write a book and take it to his library. The ruler of Pergamum is forced to find a writing material to replace papyrus and discovers parchment paper. The production of paper from calf, lamb and goat skins as a writing material was first started in the city of Pergamum in the kingdom of Pergamum in Asia Minor. It was called Pergament after the city where the paper was made. But it is paper was expensive. Nevertheless, it has several advantages over papyrus, in particular, compared to papyrus, it is more mature, flexible, can be stored for a long time, it is very convenient to write on it, it is possible to write on both sides. possible. Ordinary people could not buy this paper, and books made from it were sold at a high price. The discovery of parchment led to the replacement of scrolls made of papyrus paper with the books they look like today. Because it was discovered to prepare bound books-codexes by sewing together the pages obtained by cutting the parchment. Both papyrus and parchment were written mainly with a reed pen. 2 methods were used to prepare the ink stick. Papyrus was written with what we now call ink. They wrote on parchment paper in black ink. The process of preparing ink and ink was so perfect that a text written on papyrus thousands of years ago can still be read as it was. These inks have not lost their quality no matter how much time has passed.

The results of the research conducted by the orientalist Kasimjon Sadikov show that the wrapping paper form of book making was popular among the ancient Turks, especially in Moni communities, and large-scale Moni monuments were made in this way. Buddhists also used the wrapping paper method. It also existed in Sughd literature. It is clear from this that this type of literature has a territorial nature and was created under the influence of the mutual cultural relations of the peoples of Central Asia.⁴ Eastern literature has a special and unique place in the cultural development of the world. The formation and development of book art in the Ancient East, particularly in Central Asia, is inextricably linked with the establishment of paper production in this region for the first time in the Eastern world. It is known from sources that the discovery of paper in China in the 2nd century AD and the beginning of its production spurred the rapid development of the art of reading on a global scale. No matter how secret the production of paper, which is considered a profitable industry for the Chinese, began to be made in Samarkand from the second half of the 8th century, with the same quality as Chinese paper. Because Samarkand had all kinds of raw materials needed for paper production - silk, cotton, hemp, reed, straw, mulberry bark, etc. Regarding the types of paper made in Samarkand, *Samarkand paper* or *Sharqona paper* terms are used. In this way, the quality and elegance of the type of paper known as Samarkand paper spread to the world in a short time.⁵

⁴ Sadikov Q. From the history of Turkish writing. Ancient written monuments.T. The writer. 2000.

⁵ Barthold V.V. Turkestan until the Mongol invasion. Prepared by: Hakki Dursun Yildiz - Ankara, 1990.

You can find different opinions about the creation of Samarkand paper in historical sources. According to the sources, in the 7th century, while papyrus and parchment were still being used as the main writing materials in Europe, paper production had already started in Eastern countries. This created a wide opportunity for the spread of handwritten books in all countries belonging to the Arab caliphate, especially in the current Central Asian regions. The fact that the highest quality paper was produced in Damascus, and that the first Arab paper book that has reached us and is called the Damascus (rolling) book, is supported by evidence in historical sources. According to some scholars, paper production existed in the territory of Central Asia, especially in Samarkand, even before the Arab Caliphate.⁶ In other sources, it is said that the people of Samarkand learned the secrets of paper production from Chinese paper masters. According to P. D. Zotov's information, in July 751, Ziad ibn Salih's troops won over the Chinese army led by Gao-Xian-Zhi. As a result of the battle, 50,000 Chinese fighters were killed and 20,000 soldiers were captured. It is said that among those captured there were artisans who knew how to make paper.⁷ In fact, the first inventors of paper are the Chinese. Chinese Sai Lunya discovers paper production in 102 AD. Some sources mention that paper was produced in China long before this date. Sai Lunya creates the first paper-making technology by summarizing and further improving these long-standing folk methods of paper production. According to him, it was possible to produce paper from mulberry bark, straw, various grasses, hemp fibers, and rags. But the main raw material of Chinese paper was the bark of various trees, mainly mulberry. Chinese paper was also very popular in the world, but Samarkand paper was superior and more expensive than Samarkand paper because it could be written on both sides. It is known that because the Chinese wrote mainly with a brush, the paper made was designed for this, that is, one side of the paper was smoothed. The second side was not treated, because when writing with a brush, the ink went to the back of the paper. In this regard, Samarkand paper was more mature than Chinese paper.

According to V. V. Barthold, according to the research conducted by the Turkish historian and scientist, professor Karabajek, the production of paper from old uvada or rags is interpreted as a discovery of Samarkand people. Because it is recognized that the production of paper from uvada was started in Samarkand until the 10th century, more precisely, before 940. However, some sources state that the technology of making paper from uvada has existed in China since the second century AD. It is clear that by the end of the 10th century, Samarkand paper completely replaced papyrus and parchment in Islamic countries.⁸ Samarkand managed to publish its paper in other regions of the caliphate. Papermaking was a very profitable industry. "Indeed, Samarkand provided paper to the scribes and penmen of the entire caliphate at that time." In addition, paper trade was carried out with Europeans through the Great Silk Road. Because paper production had not yet been established in all of Europe until the 12th-13th centuries. The supply of Samarkand type of paper to the European market has

⁶ Katsprjak E.I. History book. - M.:1964.

⁷ Zotov P.T. On the history of paper production in the East // Proceedings of the Institute of Oriental Studies. Issue 3. Publishing house of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan, 1954.

⁸ Barthold V.V. Turkestan until the Mongol invasion. Prepared by: Hakki Dursun Yildiz - Ankara, 1990.

led to the replacement of papyrus, leather, and parchment, which were previously used as the main materials for writing there, and this is a significant impetus for the rise of the material and cultural development of not only Europe, but the whole world. It has been. Papers made in Samarkand are known worldwide. According to their types, such terms as Samarkand paper, Sultani paper, and Khorasan paper were used in relation to them. In this regard, the great artist-calligrapher Sultan Ali Mashhadi, who received his assessment from the great poets and thinkers of his time, Alisher Navoi and Abdurrahman Jami, writes: "No matter how much you try, there is nothing better than Chinese paper. But Samarkand paper is priceless. If you are a smart person, do not give up on it, the writing on it will be smooth and beautiful, but it must be white and clean. Whether it is simple or "sultan", try to get a good one" Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur writes about the definition of Samarkand paper: "The best paper in the world is produced by Samarkand, and all Juwazi papers come from Konigil. I am on the shore of Konigil Siyohob, this black water is called Obirihmat. In the past, water mills adapted for paper production were called juvozi paper. Samarkand has gained worldwide fame for more than a thousand years with its high-quality paper. Only after the conquest of Central Asia by Czarist Russia, paper production in Samarkand was stopped. In Central Asia, in addition to Samarkand, paper was also produced in the cities of Bukhara, Kokand and the villages located around them. Hungarian scientist Herman Vambery writes the following about the paper made in Bukhara: "The fame of writing paper made in Bukhara spread not only to Turkestan, but also to neighboring countries. These papers are made of silk, and with their smoothness and delicacy, they are very convenient for Arabic writing." At the end of the 19th century, paper was produced only in the city of Kokand in Central Asia. According to the Russian scientist V.G. Grigoryev, until 1924, special objuvoz were used in the production of paper in Kokand. Paper was produced in the city of Kokhan, as well as in the surrounding villages of Khagozgar and Chorku. The inscriptions and elegant miniatures written on these papers have not lost their value and beauty to this day. The preservation of the work for years also depends on carefully prepared paper materials

References:

1. Rustamov M. Uzbek book. T. Uzbekistan. 1968.
2. Madraimov A. The manuscripts of Alisher Navoi's works are an important source of the history of Central Asian literature in the 15th-16th centuries. History of science. dr. diss. abstract. T. 2002.
3. Sadikov Q. From the history of Turkish writing. Ancient written monuments. T. The writer. 2000.
4. Barthold V.V. Turkestan until the Mongol invasion. Prepared by: Hakki Dursun Yildiz - Ankara, 1990.
5. Katsprjak E.I. History book. - M.: 1964.
6. Ismoilova E.M. Manuscript book of Central Asia of the late period. Decoration techniques and illustrations. Abstract of the dissertation of Doctor of Historical Sciences. T. 1990.
7. Zotov P.T. On the history of paper production in the East // Proceedings of the Institute of Oriental Studies. Issue 3. Publishing house of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan, 1954.
8. Mukminova R.G. On the history of Samarkand paper production in the 16th century. // History of material culture of Uzbekistan. - T.: Science, 1964.